

Deliverable 1.6

Updated and final version of all instruments and tools

Work package	WP1
Lead- beneficiary	VU
WP Leader	Barbara Regeer
Relevant Task	Task 1.5 Adaptation of methods and tools to guide action planning and training in labs (M10-36) Task 1.7 Scaling up and continuity (M16-M36)
Participants	OSLO, AIT, IrsiCaixa, ZON, Ecsite, EUFIC (WP7)
Dissemination Level	Public
Due Date (month)	M36

Please Note: This Deliverable also encapsulates the work that in the Description of Action (DoA) of FIT4FOOD2030 was planned as Deliverable 8.3 (“Toolbox for integrated reflexive M&E in R&I development”). This toolbox for integrated reflexive monitoring and evaluation is integrated with the work of Deliverable 1.6, and the associated tools are presented in the Knowledge Hub.

Disclaimer: Currently (M36, October 2020) the Knowledge Hub and the accompanying repository for Tools for Transformation are still under construction. Several tools based on deliverables that are due in the final months of the project will be added to the Knowledge Hub at a later stage. The database of tools is continuously updated accordingly. In the final months of the project, some minor edits to the website and interface will also be made based on user experiences, to enhance the user-friendliness and visual appeal of the Knowledge Hub.

Document History and Information

VERSION	DATE	DESCRIPTION AND COMMENTS	AUTHOR
1.0	October 13, 2020	Initial Draft	Marjoleine van der Meij, Kris Kok and Barbara Regeer on behalf of WP1
	October 13-20, 2020	Feedback from Partners	Rosina Malagrida, Marina Pino, Cristina Paca, Iva Doric, Raymond Gemen
	October 13-20, 2020	Internal Project Review	Jonas Lazaro Mojica (on behalf of F4L) and Chrissie Brierley (on behalf of ZON).
1.1	October 23, 2020	Second Draft	Kris Kok on behalf of WP1
	October 28, 2020	Project Coordinator Review	Jacqueline Broerse, Coordinator
Final	October 30, 2020	Final Version	Kris Kok on behalf of WP1

Introduction

This deliverable describes the work carried out under the umbrella of the Working Group on Tools for Transformation, established within the FIT4FOOD2030 project. The goal of this working group was to collect all the tools that have been developed throughout the project, and to make them available online on an engaging platform in suitable formats to be used by a wide range of stakeholders interested in the role of R&I in food system transformation, such as researchers, policy makers, innovators and educators. For an overview of the different purposes of the tools, see Figure 1.

The result of these efforts is the FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub. It can be accessed through: <https://knowledgehub.fit4food2030.eu/>

The Knowledge Hub already contains over 80 tools, including training programs, short exercises and communication materials. While the Working Group on Tools for Transformation operated under Work Package 1 (WP1, “Methodology to build the FOOD2030 Platform”), the website development efforts were led by WP7 (“Communication, dissemination and future engagement”) and the tools themselves are developed by many different partners in the project.

As the finalization of the Knowledge Hub is still work in progress until the end of the project (December 2020) and the Knowledge Hub itself represents Deliverable 1.6 (updated and final version of all instruments and tools), this document only describes the key features of the (process towards developing the) Knowledge Hub. Please refer to the Knowledge Hub to review the contents of this deliverable.

Figure 1: Overview of the many possible purposes of the different FIT4FOOD2030 tools.

The Process of Developing the Tools

The tools for stimulating interactions on the role of R&I in food system transformation were developed across the different WPs of FIT4FOOD2030. Most tools were applied, thereby ‘tested’, either during training sessions with project partners, or in lab activities with stakeholders, or both. Based on the feedback of the participants and experience of the facilitators, the tools were updated and improved. This iterative process of tool testing and tool adaptation will continue until the end of the project.

In an effort to coordinate and advance the development, alignment and dissemination of tools developed in the project, FIT4FOOD2030 established the Working Group on Tools for Transformation in September 2019. The establishment of the Working Group enabled WP1 and the other WPs to further mobilize the project’s collective capacity to further develop (materials in to) transformative tools.

The concepts ‘tool’ and ‘toolbox’ were developed further in a collaborative effort by the Consortium partners during an interactive workshop at the Consortium Meeting on October 17, 2019 in Brussels. This workshop was organized by WP1 in collaboration with the partners from WP8 (“Learning for transformation”). During the workshop, requirements were formulated for the FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub on three levels in an attempt to answer three guiding questions:

1. structure of the Knowledge Hub (“How does the Knowledge Hub look like”)
2. tools (“What are the Tools?”)
3. user experiences (“Who is going to use the Knowledge Hub and how?”)

A second workshop from the Tools for Transformation working group took place during the online Consortium Meeting on March 31, 2020. As part of the workshop, a session was organized on “Translating Materials to Tools”, related to another session organized by WP7 on “Communication and Dissemination”. During these sessions participants addressed the question how all the different materials developed within the project could be translated in to tools. Furthermore, they validated and adapted a first draft of the structure of the platform and it’s key features, and also.

Developing Templates for Different Tools for Transformation

Building on the results of these workshops, the Working Group collected all the tools developed in the project so far and made a uniform template for all the tools, see Figure 2. The scope of application for each tool is wider than the original test setting – food system transformation – only. The partners responsible for the deliverable or material that formed the basis for the specific tool, filled in the template. In developing the final version of the different ‘tools’, FIT4FOOD2030 partners sought a balance between being very specific in terms of instructions on the one hand, but also to facilitate degrees of freedom, to allow for more general applicability of the tools for various types of system change facilitation worldwide.

Figure 2: The FIT4FOOD2030 tool-format design characteristics.

In total, the Working Group developed templates for five different types of tools (see Figure 3):

1. Educational modules (15 tools)
2. Training and reflection modules for professionals and stakeholders (21 tools)
3. Short exercises for collaborative deliberation, reflection and co-creation (25 tools)
4. Data sets and related materials (4 tools)
5. Communication Tools (20 tools).

Figure 3: Overview of the 5 different tool-types in the FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub.

A Knowledge Hub with Tools for Transformation

So far, 85 different tools have been developed. The finalized FIT4FOOD2030 tools are collected in an open-access online [Knowledge Hub](#) designed to be expanded with more tools for various contexts. The [Tools for Transformation database](#) is designed for people that want to take a (leading) role in system transformation, with an explicit link to R&I. While the tools have been designed in the context of food systems R&I, some of them are transferable to other systems as well.

The Knowledge Hub provides access to the tools via four gateways (see Figure 4) that each represent one challenge that the anticipated users are confronted with:

1) [I would like to run a food lab or living lab. What do I do?](#)

This gateway reveals tools that can help in setting-up and running a lab, from network building to activity organizing, such as visioning.

2) [I would like to explore and understand the food system.](#)

This gateway shows tools that can help to overview a specific (local) food system, in terms of e.g. trends, stakeholders, and research and innovation.

3) [I would like to improve R&I policy coherence and alignment.](#)

This gateway contains tools that guide policy-related system transformation, in particular in research and innovation in food systems, or beyond.

4) [I would like to educate or train people on food system transformation.](#)

This gateway provides a large collection of educational modules that help to build competencies for (food) system transformation among youngsters, students and professionals.

I would like to run a **food lab** or **living lab**. What do I do?

[FIND RESOURCES](#)

I would like to **explore** and **understand the food system**

[FIND RESOURCES](#)

I would like to improve **R&I policy coherence and alignment**

[FIND RESOURCES](#)

I would like to **educate or train people** on food system transformation

[FIND RESOURCES](#)

Figure 4: Overview of the user interface of the FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub. There are four different gateways to ‘enter’ the repository of tools (bottom), each filtering the tools relevant for the kind of activity the user wants to explore.

User and Usage Scenario

Central to developing these four gateways, were the Working Group's efforts to develop stakeholder narratives and to understand the variety of rationales that different stakeholders might have for accessing the Knowledge Hub. Developing user stories or narratives of imaginary 'target stakeholders' is a means of opening up creative thinking about the different ways stakeholders can experience and use the tools. As such, it is an important step in the design process towards a user-friendly Knowledge Hub. One of such (imaginary) 'target stakeholders' and its narrative was Giorgio (see Box 1).

About Giorgio...

Giorgio is educational program manager of a science museum. After many years of designing exhibits, tours and educational packages for schools, Giorgio has convinced the museum board to create a museum-led **platform** that intensifies connections between the museum and its direct surrounding. Giorgio's museum is located in a city bordering on a large natural forest on the one side and agricultural land and industry on the other side, in which a lot of food-related activities take place. The city region is facing major challenges such as pollution and depletion due to these activities. Therefore, Giorgio decides that the platform should focus on facilitating food system transformation.

Giorgio is ambitious. On the one hand, he wants to **connect stakeholders** to the platform and **organize catalyzing events**. On the other hand Giorgio aims to **align** the platform activities with the 'educational assortment' in the museum, and (even) incite **action planning in the municipality**. Moreover, along the way of setting up and running the 'platform to be', Giorgio hopes that all actors (including himself and his board) take a **reflexive stance** in what they are doing, to learn from their experiences, from one another and from stakeholders, and thereby optimize the platform to the needs of all actors involved.

One morning, Giorgio searches the World Wide Web for resources and guides on how to do this... Amongst the search results, he encounters the FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub and its various tools....

Giorgio's experience with the FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub...

A Knowledge Hub user like Giorgio clicks, for example, on the Tools for Transformation gateway '*I would like to run a food lab or living lab. What do I do?*' Scrolling through the tools that are part of this gateway Giorgio **selects keywords** that relate to him, to find more specific tools for his specific needs and questions (see Figure 5). This keyword search is possible in each gateway. After **scrolling and playing** around with various keyword combinations, Giorgio selects the Stakeholder Analysis tool (see Figure 6). With the help of this tool, Giorgio invites colleagues in a stakeholder mapping session for decision making on who the museum-led platform should invite to its first year of events. When he opens the Stakeholder Analysis tool on the Knowledge Hub, Giorgio will also see other **related tools**. With another tool, for example the Citizen Consultation format, **Giorgio organizes in-museum activities** that align with the platform's activities, and he uses the Dynamic Learning Agenda tool (DLA) as support in facilitating reflection among all stakeholders included so far. After using the tools, Giorgio leaves a comment for each tool on the Knowledge Hub, **sharing his experiences** with the other (future) users of the Knowledge Hub.

Box 1: Introducing Giorgio, a potential user of the FIT4FOOD2030 Knowledge Hub.

Search...

I Want To Engage

- Researchers (32)
- Facilitators (31)
- Policy makers (31)
- Professionals (28)
- Funders (24)
- Non Governmental Organisations / Civil Society Organisations (24)
- Businesses (23)
- Students (23)
- NGO/CSO (5)
- Intermediaries of food system transformation (4)

[See 3 more](#)

Keywords

- Multi-stakeholder approach (30)
- Digital-proof tool (27)
- Food system approach (25)
- Co-creation (21)
- Innovation (19)

DATA SETS AND RELATED MATERIALS

Mapping EU Food System Policies

Mapping EU Food System Policies

FIT4FOOD2030 has mapped out current EU and national food system-related policies, classified according to FOOD 2030 priorities, policy goals...

TRAINING AND REFLECTION MODULE

Food Lab Design

Lab design

Would you like to set-up a multi-stakeholder platform, network, or lab for food system transformation? This document provides a guideline for setting up a 'lab' that...

TRAINING AND REFLECTION MODULE

Designing multi-stakeholder events

Designing multi-stakeholder events

Do you want to facilitate food system transformation by means of engaging (super) diverse actors? This document provides inspiration...

TRAINING AND REFLECTION MODULE

Citizen consultation on food system transformation

SHORT EXERCISES

Co-designing educational modules

SHORT EXERCISES

Visioning on the role of R&I for future-proof systems

Figure 5: The first tools that show up when clicking on the gateway 'I would like to run a food lab or living lab. What do I do?' All tools are 'click-able'. Once clicked, the tool-page - with tool-specific details and the PDF file - opens in a new tab; see for example the Stakeholder Analysis tool in Figure 6.

Tools for transformation About Contact

Lab design

In a nutshell

Would you like to set-up a multi-stakeholder platform, network, or lab for food system transformation? This document provides a guideline for setting up a 'lab' that acts as a facilitator for food system transformation in a specific local context.

What for?

The guideline helps you to work with communities

For whom?

Intermediaries of change / food system transformation

How long?

Applying the guideline can take several hours to months or years

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Download the lab design script below:

[DOWNLOAD](#)

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Figure 6: The details and PDF of the Stakeholder Analysis tool, opened in a new tab.

Knowledge Hub Sustainability

The Knowledge Hub will remain up and running in its current form until three years after the end of FIT4FOOD2030 (December 2023). After that, FIT4FOOD2030's coordinating partner VU (Athena Institute) will permanently host and update the Knowledge Hub in accordance to newly gained experiences and insights in these newer projects.

Currently, FIT4FOOD2030 is working to ensure that the Tools for Transformation in the Knowledge Hub can inform the work in future (EU-funded) projects, as well as for instance the EU Partnership on "Safe and Sustainable Food Systems for People, Planet and Climate".

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